

How to Select, Configure and Install ESM Software Stacks

Handbook for System Administrators: Specification of a standard recommendation for an ESM System Software Stack

Deliverable D3.5

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Lead author:

Barcelona Supercomputing Center (BSC), Kim Serradell

Other contributing authors:

Max-Planck-Institut für Meteorologie (MPI-M), Reinhard Budich, Sergey Kosukhin

Barcelona Supercomputing Center (BSC), Kim Serradell

The University of Reading (UREAD), Grenville Lister

Contacts: esiwace@dkrz.de

Visit us on: www.esiwace.eu

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1. Abstract /publishable summary

Nowadays, to build, run and configure up-to-date weather and climate models it takes more components than solely the source codes. Models are subject to a long list of dependencies in the form of libraries, open source and/or commercial software packages or many other pieces of software such as system utilities. These requirements make the life of system administrators in HPC centres hard. When a new user gets resources on a specific platform, it will take time before the actual simulations can start, because platform related problems with models and software need to be solved first.

The aim of this deliverable is to explain the methodology to select, configure and install a complete ESM software stack in a handbook. This handbook is intended to ease the deployment of models and to reduce the time to start simulations at an HPC facility. The time to solution from idea to published result should thus be substantially reduced. Ideally, following the guidelines in this document, the centres willing to run weather and climate models will be prepared to offer all the tools required by these models, and their users, the scientists.

As a matter of precision, in this document we do not define the software stack needed for a centre to run weather and climate models. This definition comes from the deliverable D3.1¹.

2. Conclusion & Results

The main result of the deliverable is the publication of the first version of the: *Handbook for System Administrators: Specification of a standard recommendation for an ESM System Software Stack*. This version will be available on the ESIWACE website www.esiwace.eu.

The handbook contains:

- requirements that ESM workflows pose to HPC environments, as well as recommendations and best practices to fulfil them;
- list of the system software that is common for ESM workflows;
- description of tools that allow for automatization of the system software deployment.

3. Project objectives

This deliverable contributes directly and indirectly to the achievement of all the macro-objectives and specific goals indicated in section 1.1 of the Description of Action:

Macro-objectives	Contribution of this deliverable?
Improve the efficiency and productivity of numerical weather and climate simulation on high-performance computing platforms	YES
Support the end-to-end workflow of global Earth system modelling for weather and climate simulation in high performance computing environments	YES
The European weather and climate science community will drive the governance structure that defines the services to be provided by ESIWACE	NO

¹ ESIWACE Application Software Framework: A White Paper. Version 1: Specification of a Standard Recommendation for an End-to-end Workflows and Application Software Environments Framework

Foster the interaction between industry and the weather and climate community on the exploitation of high-end computing systems, application codes and services.	NO
Increase competitiveness and growth of the European HPC industry	NO

Specific goals in the workplan	Contribution of this deliverable?
Provide services to the user community that will impact beyond the lifetime of the project.	YES
Improve scalability and shorten the time-to-solution for climate and operational weather forecasts at increased resolution and complexity to be run on future extreme-scale HPC systems.	YES
Foster usability of the available tools, software, computing and data handling infrastructures.	YES
Pursue exploitability of climate and weather model results.	NO
Establish governance of common software management to avoid unnecessary and redundant development and to deliver the best available solutions to the user community.	YES
Provide open access to research results and open source software at international level.	YES
Exploit synergies with other relevant activities and projects and also with the global weather and climate community	YES

4. Detailed report on the deliverable

The Handbook for system administrators: Specification of a standard recommendation for an ESM System Software Stack is contained in the Annex 1 to this deliverable.

5. References (*Bibliography*)

- Petar Forai, Kenneth Hoste, Guilherme Peretti-Pezzi, Brett Bode 2016. [Making Scientific Software Installation Reproducible On Cray Systems Using EasyBuild](#). In *Proceedings of the Cray User Group 2016 (CUG'2016)*.
- Markus Geimer, Kenneth Hoste, and Robert McLay. 2014. [Modern scientific software management using EasyBuild and Lmod](#). In *Proceedings of the First International Workshop on HPC User Support Tools (HUST '14)*. IEEE Press, Piscataway, NJ, USA, 41-51. DOI=<http://dx.doi.org/10.1109/HUST.2014.8>
- Kenneth Hoste, Jens Timmerman, Andy Georges, and Stijn De Weirdt. 2012. [EasyBuild: Building Software with Ease](#). In *Proceedings of the 2012 SC Companion: High Performance Computing, Networking Storage and Analysis (SCC '12)*. IEEE Computer Society, Washington, DC, USA, 572-582. DOI=<http://dx.doi.org/10.1109/SC.Companion.2012.81>

6. Dissemination and uptake

6.1 Dissemination

The handbook will be published on the ESIWACE website and advertised in ESIWACE presentations and publications.

6.2 Uptake by the targeted audience

As indicated in the Description of the Action, the audience for this deliverable is:

X	The general public (PU)
	The project partners, including the Commission services (PP)
	A group specified by the consortium, including the Commission services (RE)
	This reports is confidential, only for members of the consortium, including the Commission services (CO)

This is how we are going to ensure the uptake of the deliverables by the targeted audience

The attached Handbook will be updated regularly. Information about the updates will be disseminated through the regular channels: project webpages, workshops and citations.

7. The delivery is delayed: Yes No

The project was rescheduled to an earlier starting date. The summer school organizers decided to have the school already in June 2016 – instead of September as originally planned. Furthermore, it was decided, due to the resulting lack of time, to run the different models at different centres, thus rendering it less necessary to invest into model porting, which is kind of the basic assumption to be the major obstacle for good usability of climate models.

Also, there has been a change of the tools used to deliver the solutions explained in this document. At the start of the project, EasyBuild² was used. Technical difficulties with this tool necessitated a switch to the Spack tool³. So many of the tasks needed to be re-engineered.

8. Changes made and/or difficulties encountered, if any

See text above.

9. Efforts for this deliverable

Person-months spent on this deliverable:

Beneficiary	Person-months	Period covered	Names of scientists involved, including third parties (if appropriate)

² <https://hpcugent.github.io/easybuild/>

³ <http://spack.readthedocs.io/en/latest/>

			and their gender (f/m)
DKRZ			
ECMWF			
CNRS-IPSL			
MPG	2	1 September 2015 - today	R. Budich (m), S. Kosukhin (m)
CERFACS			
BSC	3	1 September 2015- today	K. Serradell (m), O. Mulla-Valls (m)
STFC			
MET O			
UREAD	1	1 September 2015- today	G. Lister (m)
SMHI			
ICHEC			
CMCC			
DWD			
SEAGATE			
BULL			
ALLINEA			
Total	6		

10. Sustainability

10.1. Lessons learnt: both positive and negative that can be drawn from the experiences of the work to date

Very cooperative mood between the centres, quite clear setting for the goals, and good understanding for the usefulness of the approach.

10.2 Links built with other deliverables, WPs, and synergies created with other projects

This deliverable will take as input the list of software defined by D3.1.

Links with other WPs: The models used up to now for deploying the methodology are models used in the Scalability WP2. In this sense, the work done is expected to be very useful for the other partners.

Concerning WP1, we plan for strong interaction concerning the listed community software and the list of tools used to install and configure the software stack. Also, the list will be communicated to PRACE and Tier0 and Tier1 centres.

11. Dissemination activities

Peer-review articles

Not applicable yet.

Intellectual property rights resulting from this deliverable

Not applicable.

Handbook for System Administrators

**A Living Document on the
Specification of a Standard Recommendation
for an ESM System Software Stack**

Kim Serradell
Sergey Kosukhin
Grenville Lister
Reinhard Budich

Introduction

This document provides guidelines for system administrators and advanced users to support their efforts in preparation of supercomputing environments for Earth System Modelling (ESM) experiments. Along with the general recommendations on system configuration, this document contains information on the system software stack that is common and required for most ESM workflows.

It also traces our research on better and easier ways to build a complete software stack for the Earth System community. We present not only our solutions but also the approaches that we have discarded due to various reasons.

We also want this document to become a starting point for collaboration between users and system administrators. The former are expected to refer to this document to get indications on what problems need to be solved and what questions need to be posed to fill the gap between the system software stack that is available on the system they use and the stack that is necessary to run their experiments.

It should be noted that HPC environments can be configured following very different approaches and usage policies, thus not all the presented recommendations might be applicable to a particular case. This document will be kept updated over the next years, which means that some solutions presented here can evolve or get discarded during time.

Job submission policies

In this section, we will describe the schedulers deployed by the partners and use their experiences to recommend a configuration for an ESM environment.

Different schedulers are on the market. There are commercial and free solutions. We will compare the usage of commercial ones (LSF from IBM) with a free open source solution, SLURM. The recommendations below are based on the experience of the Earth System department at Barcelona Supercomputing Center BSC, where the HPC system Mare Nostrum is used in both operational and research mode.

Testbed partitions

ESM models are complex pieces of software that are sensitive to many factors and typically require a significant degree of tuning in order to develop optimal scientific and computational configurations to capture desired physical processes and to maximize efficient throughput. Testing and tuning need to be undertaken in respect of, for example, compiler options, processor decomposition, load balancing, pre and post processing workflow, in a development environment for fast turnaround and consequently, it is recommended to provide users with small partitions that allow allocating only several nodes for a short period but have high priority. This enables intensive and timely testing to be undertaken prior to running the experiments in production.

Task prioritisation

A common practice for ESM workflow implementation is to split simulation periods into smaller chunks (usually from one to ten years of model time) and submit them to the scheduler as sequential jobs. The main reason for this is to keep the job chains running in case of hard- or software failures (that are expected to become rather the rule than exception at exascale), and to prevent wasting significant amounts of CPU time that otherwise would be necessary to rerun calculations from the initial state. This approach also allows a straightforward solution to running post-processing tasks simultaneously with the model and thus enhances parallelism. To support this well-established practice, it is highly

recommended to adjust job scheduling rules to allow for repetitive job submissions from the same user by disabling possible priority penalties. Ideally, if one job is finished the next one that appears in the job queue within a minute should get the released resources⁴.

Service nodes

We recommend providing users with information on the mechanisms of job submission. Commands for job submission and control should be easily identified and explained (in the user guide of the facility) and we recommend using the default commands and avoiding changes in the binaries.

If the cluster has dedicated service nodes different than compute nodes, this should be indicated to the user. Build procedures can differ for these nodes and compilation scripts have to be modified to reflect the differences.

For example, a user wants to run one of the MPI-ESM1's post-processing scripts that calls the CDOs. She submits the script through SLURM and requests a single node for it. If the HPC she works with is Mistral then everything works well, because the script is executed directly on the first (and single) allocated compute node. But if it's a Cray supercomputer, then the script is executed by a service node and the CDOs are also executed on a service node (but not on the allocated compute node), which is already wrong (service nodes should not be loaded by applications). More than that, a service node can have a different processor, which means that CDOs must be compiled for a different processor architecture. So, what we ask here for is to give our users information on how scripts they submit will be executed by an HPC. With this information, they will be able to modify their scripts to use HPC properly.

Storage policies

ESM experiments require huge disk space. Increasing resolution, number of model components, larger ensemble sizes and higher numbers of variables stored all contribute to increasing the volume of disk space needed to perform experiments. In this sense, some recommendations adapted to ESM simulations can be formulated to make a better use of the storage. In this analysis, we identify three different kinds of storage, used for different stages of the simulation, where each one has different policies.

- **Model filesystem:** the place where the simulation is run and where the outputs are generated. This partition should only be used to produce the results and never used to store outputs. In this sense, a recommendation (quite aggressive) is to delete files not used after a defined time. This can have a critical impact in new users but avoids wasting space. This filesystem needs to be fast, reliable and scalable.
- **Post-process filesystem:** once the simulation is performed, outputs (or a selection of outputs) are moved to this partition for the analysis and the exploitation of results. This is done with post-processing tools and it's recommended to have an organized storage of the data using ids for experiments. In this stage, usually conversion of file type or computations of new indexes are performed.
- **Long term storage:** once the simulation has been processed, results extracted and usually published by scientists, results needs to be stored for some years to be accessed again if revision is needed. In this case, instant access is not needed therefore, tapes are a good solution for this storage.

System software

Our experience shows that it is often hard to strictly distinguish between application software, which is expected to be handled by users and system software, which should be deployed and maintained by system administrators of an HPC facility (see Figure 1). In the

⁴ The recommendation is implemented at DKRZ

scope of this document we define *application software* as software that users directly work with and *system software* as software that users do not have to know about but is essential for their workflows and also is not too domain-specific to expect a system administrator to be ready to maintain it.

The SW-Stacks

1st EsiWACE Review, 08.04.2016

Figure 1: Application and system software stacks.

Depending on many factors (e.g. the primary scientific domain, hardware architecture, operating system, etc.), supercomputing facilities have different policies on what software is available to their users by default, and approaches to how that is implemented. It should be also noted that the default software stack often contains custom optimised versions of the commonly used libraries. This has to be taken into account during the application deployment process. That is why users should be provided with a common point, from which they can start working with an HPC system. This point could be a web based set of Frequently Asked Questions (FAQ) or a complete User Guide.

For ESMs, a good practice is having the models (if it's a common model well known and used by the community), already installed and built appropriately for the infrastructure (using the most suitable compilers and flags to get the best performance possible) in the common software folders. Not all ESMs exhibit the same degree of sensitivity to HPC configuration; some of them are not dependent on the configuration, and in such cases one build satisfies all needs (FAMOUS is such an example with very little dependence on the HPC environment.) This central installation can also provide standard submission infrastructure and test jobs to make the deployment easier and safer for the user.

This section contains a list of system software including recommendations on how to install and configure them. Users need information on where this software is installed in the system, how to use it, and what the corresponding known issues are, as well as the recommended ways to overcome them.

Environment modules

The best way to enable users to adjust software environments to their needs is to install and configure an Environment Module system.

The Environment Modules package provides dynamic modification of a user's environment via module files. Each module file contains the information needed to configure the shell for an application. Once the modules package is initialized, the environment can be modified on a per-module basis using the module command which interprets module files.

Typically, module files instruct the module command to alter or set shell environment variables such as PATH, MANPATH, etc. Modules can be loaded and unloaded dynamically and atomically, in a clean fashion. Modules are useful in managing different versions of applications. Modules can also be bundled into meta-modules that will load an entire suite of different applications. Also, Modules can manage incompatibilities and prevent modules from being loaded if a environment conflict could otherwise occur.

Compilers

C and Fortran compilers are required for most ESM software. We recommend providing users with several compilers from different vendors (GNU, Intel, Cray, etc.) to allow for workarounds that might be necessary if a particular piece of software does not work when compiled with one of them. This approach of providing users with different choices should also be applied to the compiler versions. Some codes do not run correctly with some specific version of a compiler. System administrators should update (but also preserve) versions of the same compiler, and make older versions accessible.

We strongly recommend to configure compilers using modules. The user will be able to identify all the compilers and versions available in the system and will not have to take care of the many variables defined by compilers.

Libraries and utilities

Many of the problems encountered when deploying an ESM are related to libraries. To address these common and repeated issues we have put our efforts into the development of recommendations and procedures that help to overcome them and reduce the time to deploy and run a model.

Below, we provide a list of software that is common for most of the ESM applications. Some elements of the list depend on other elements, thus forming a set of tree structures. The pieces of software should be installed one by one in the order from the roots to the leaves of the trees. The list is not closed or even comprehensive yet. So, we expect it to grow in the course of the development of this handbook.

NetCDF

Description: NetCDF (network Common Data Form) is a set of interfaces for array-oriented data access and a freely-distributed collection of data access libraries for C, Fortran, C++, Java, and other languages. The NetCDF libraries support a machine-independent format for representing scientific data. Together, the interfaces, libraries, and format support the creation, access, and sharing of scientific data.

Homepage: <http://www.unidata.ucar.edu/software/netcdf/>

NetCDF-C

Description: C interface to the NetCDF library.

Required version: 4.2 or newer

Dependencies: hdf5

Known issues: NetCDF library 4.4.0 or earlier, combined with libhdf5 1.10.0 or greater, will generate NetCDF-4 format files that cannot be read by software using earlier versions of libhdf5 (1.8.x), regardless of the version of NetCDF.

Building system: Autotools or CMake

Mandatory configure options: enable-netcdf4

Name in Spack repository: netcdf

NetCDF-Fortran

Description: Fortran interface to the NetCDF library.

Required version: 4.4.3 or newer

Dependencies: NetCDF-C

Building system: Autotools or CMake

Name in Spack repository: netcdf-fortran

NetCDF-CXX

Description: Legacy C++ interface to the NetCDF library.

Required version: 4.2 or newer in this branch (NetCDF-CXX4 is not backwards compatible).

Dependencies: NetCDF-C

Building system: Autotools

Known issues: This version of the NetCDF C++ library includes no changes since the 4.1.3 release, but is provided for backwards compatibility as a separate package. It was developed before key C++ concepts such as templates, namespaces, and exceptions were widely supported. It is not recommended for new projects, but it still works. A newer version is available, but not necessary for the configurations considered here.

Name in Spack repository: netcdf-cxx

HDF5

Description: Data model, library, and file format for storing and managing data. It supports an unlimited variety of data types, and is designed for flexible and efficient I/O and for high volume and complex data.

Homepage: <https://support.hdfgroup.org/HDF5/>

Required version: 1.8.12 or newer in this branch (see known issues for NetCDF-C)

Dependencies: szip

Building system: Autotools

Name in Spack repository: hdf5

Python

Description: General-purpose, interpreted programming language.

Required version: 2.7 or newer in this branch.

Homepage: <http://python.org>

Name in Spack repository: python

Jinja2

Description: Jinja2 is a template engine written in pure Python.

Extension homepage: <http://jinja.pocoo.org/>

Name in Spack repository: py-jinja2

NetCDF4-Python

Description: Python interface to the NetCDF Library.

Extension homepage: <http://unidata.github.io/netcdf4-python/>

Name in Spack repository: py-netcdf

NumPy

Description: NumPy is the fundamental package for scientific computing with Python.

Extension homepage: <http://www.numpy.org/>

Name in Spack repository: py-numpy

CDO

Description: CDO is a collection of command line Operators to manipulate and analyse Climate and NWP model Data.

Homepage: <https://code.zmaw.de/projects/cdo>

Required version: 1.7.2

Dependencies: netcdf, grib-api, hdf5, udunits2

Name in Spack repository: cdo

NCO

Description: The NCO toolkit manipulates and analyzes data stored in netCDF-accessible format.

Homepage: <http://nco.sourceforge.net/>

Required version: 4.6.3

Dependencies: netcdf, udunits2, antlr

Name in Spack repository: nco

NCL

Description: NCL is an interpreted language designed specifically for scientific data analysis and visualization

Homepage: <https://www.ncl.ucar.edu/>

Required version: 6.3.0

Dependencies: netcdf, hdf5, udunits2

Name in Spack repository: ncl

EXTRAE

Description: Extrae is the package devoted to generate tracefiles which can be analysed later by Paraver. Extrae is a tool that uses different interposition mechanisms to inject probes into the target application so as to gather information regarding the application performance.

Homepage: <https://tools.bsc.es/extrae>

Required version: 3.4.1

Dependencies: mpi, dyninst, libunwind, boost, libdwarf, papi, libelf, libxml2, binutils.

Name in Spack repository: extrae

PARAVER

Description: A very powerful performance visualization and analysis tool based on traces that can be used to analyse any information that expressed on its input trace format.

Homepage: <https://tools.bsc.es/paraver>

Required version: 4.6.2

Dependencies: boost, extrae, wx, wxpropgrid

Name in Spack repository: paraver

Automatizing software installation

Getting an ESM workflow to work in an arbitrary supercomputing environment can be tricky. Workflows usually require many pieces of software to be correctly compiled and linked. Many software dependencies have to be accounted for. There are many versions and configure options for each application, libraries and several compilers that users might want to use (e.g. to find out which one works best for their needs). All this produces a large combinatorial space to get lost in very easily. Many Linux distributions offer their users various package managers that help handle these issues.

Using such managers, users can install software they need without diving into details of software dependencies, configuration and compilation. The problem with those package managers is that usually they are designed to work in a particular well-defined and well-tested software environment (usually with a single compiler and root privileges). Such circumstances are unfortunately not given for most supercomputers.

One of the main goals of this document is to deliver a method to deploy the whole software stack and to automatize this process for an arbitrary environment as much as possible. To achieve that we have tested several tools (so called package managers) that address this issue and account for the mentioned heterogeneity of HPC systems.

EasyBuild (package manager)

Based on previous BSC experience, the EasyBuild⁵ package manager developed at Ghent University (Belgium) has been selected at first as software to automatize software installation. EasyBuild, presented at Supercomputing 2012, has been developed and improved for several years. It is available on GitHub since April 2012. Nowadays, rather than

⁵ <http://hpcugent.github.io/easybuild>

a software developed at Ghent University, it has become a community driven project. As a mature and tested tool for building software it has been chosen to become part of the OpenHPC⁶ project.

EasyBuild provides a way for compiling with the standard building tools, like autotools⁷ or CMake⁸, but also the possibility to create custom ones. The specific piece of code that allows compiling software is called, in EB terminology, easyblock. Currently available easyblocks include a set of generic building blocks like `configuremake.py`, `jar.py`, or `cmakemake.py`. The software can be extended easily to provide new blocks to build complex software like WRF (`wrf.py`).

Our experience with EasyBuild showed that even though it is a great tool, there are two serious problems that do not let us to recommend this software to the community. The first one is that the tool mainly targets system administrators of the HPC facilities who build software stacks for their system from scratch. The scenario when a regular user needs to extend or upgrade an existing software stack is almost not covered. The second issue is that the learning curve of EasyBuild is quite steep and it takes time for a developer to start implementing new recipes for packages.

Spack (package manager)

Having in mind the problems that we had encountered with EasyBuild, we started looking for alternatives. Our current recommendation is Spack⁹ – a package manager designed to be used on different supercomputers for software stack maintenance. We choose this software over other existing solutions for its flexibility and comprehensible structure of the code. The latter helped us to adjust Spack to the needs of the climate modelling community and enable automatic installation of most of the package described in the previous section.

Spack also supports the standard building systems like autotools and CMake. Custom installation scripts can be handled by implementing wrappers (packages in terms of Spack) in Python language. The installation procedure for Spack is quite simple and described in the documentation that is available on its homepage.

Developments

The selection of the tools to port to Spack has been done within the project. All the tools ported have been accepted by the Spack developers. To avoid issues with the users, an extensive automatic testing process is done before releasing a package. The work necessary to start a new package from scratch is not negligible. There are packages (like `cdo`) with more than ten dependencies in the building stage, and the procedure deployed needs to handle all of them.

To the date (2017-02-23), the following packages have been made available through Spack in the framework of the ESIWACE and are available through Spack's main repository¹⁰:

⁶ <http://www.openhpc.community>

⁷ https://www.gnu.org/software/automake/manual/html_node/Autotools-Introduction.html

⁸ <https://cmake.org>

⁹ <http://spack.readthedocs.io/en/latest>

¹⁰ <https://github.com/LLNL/spack>

- cdo: CDO is a collection of command line Operators to manipulate and analyse Climate and NWP model Data.
- cmor: Climate Model Output Rewriter is used to produce CF-compliant netCDF files. The structure of the files created by the library and the metadata they fulfil the requirements of many of the climate community's standard model experiments.
- Uuid: OSSP uuid is a ISO-C:1999 application programming interface (API) and corresponding command line interface (CLI) for the generation of DCE 1.1, ISO/IEC 11578:1996 and RFC 4122 compliant Universally Unique Identifier (UUID).
- grib-api: the ECMWF GRIB API is an application program interface accessible from C, FORTRAN and Python programs developed for encoding and decoding WMO FM-92 GRIB edition 1 and edition 2 messages.
- libemos: the Interpolation library (EMOSLIB) includes Interpolation software and BUFR & CREX encoding/decoding routines.
- magics: ECMWF's Meteorological plotting software MAGICS. Although completely redesigned in C++, it is intended to be as backwards-compatible as possible with the Fortran interface.
- ncl: an interpreted language designed specifically for scientific data analysis and visualization. Supports NetCDF 3/4, GRIB 1/2, HDF 4/5, HDF-EOD 2/5, shapefile, ASCII, binary. Numerous analysis functions are built-in.

Some other packages like harfbuzz, pango, qt, libtiff, pixman, libjpeg-turbo, gmp, python, py-netcdf, environment-modules, extrae, paraver and hdf5 have been updated to be used by the ones presented previously.

Finally, five system level updates and discussions with the core development team have been introduced in the source code of the tool.

To have a complete list of these developments, browse the code repository looking for interactions done by users [skosukhin](#) and [kserradell](#).

Known issues

Automatic software installation requires network access to download source codes. Depending on the security restrictions of the HPC system, a cluster may not have direct connection to the net, thus blocking any download and preventing the usual way of working with these tools. In these cases, the person in charge of the installation will need to manage and provide a way to download all the files on a server with connection and then copy all the files to the HPC system to continue with the installation process.

Conclusions and Outlook

The ESM community runs a large range of models on a wide variety of computational platforms, and while there has been (and continues to be) convergence in several areas (data formats, for example, and use of common components such as NEMO and XIOS, and increased centralization of data processing capability), there remains significant diversity in ESM software. Consequently, its maintenance continues to pose challenges not only to users (who, understandably, may have little interest in and particularly little time for these aspects) but also to HPC service providers. The main burden that we have to mention here is that many pieces of software that are used in the community, and ES models themselves are built with various custom utilities, which prevents application of well-established solutions for software deployment, and requires individual treatment for each of them. This increases complexity of the installation procedures dramatically, as well as time necessary to perform them. We admit that there might be good reasons for using non-standard building systems but

have to warn the community that this issue requires broader discussion and measures to be taken to reduce the existing diversity of the building systems.

Identification of software components that are common across ESM systems and the means by which they can be installed, maintained, and updated, forms a major area of work essential to the future success of ES modeling and in particular to improving the efficiency and reducing the complexity of this effort. The advantages of adopting a common software stack with documented and traceable provenance are numerous and in conjunction with the module system, it allows for faster development and debugging. Automation of the software stack installation potentially opens ES modeling to those in the community without access to HPC resources, and simplifies the role of those providing dedicated ESM support.

The work described here starts to identify the common software and suggests a tool (Spack) with which this software can be installed and maintained. We see our next task in gathering feedbacks from the community, which will help us to prioritize steps that need to be made in this direction.

This Handbook is a deliverable of the project ESIWACE www.esiwace.eu.

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